

Utilizing the Mutual Agreement Procedure in Resolving International Tax Disputes in Tanzania: Prospects and Challenges

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Abstract:

This article examines the utilization of the Mutual Agreement Procedure (MAP) in resolving tax disputes under Tanzanian Double Taxation Agreements (DTAs). The MAP, provided for under Article 25 of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) Model Tax Convention on Income and on Capital 2017, and United Nations Model Double Taxation Convention between Developed and Developing Countries, is designed to prevent double taxation and facilitate cooperation between tax authorities of treaty partners. Tanzania has concluded DTAs with several countries, including Canada, India, and South Africa, which incorporate MAP provisions. However, many of these treaties are based on outdated models that do not reflect modern international standards such as the OECD's 2012 Manual on Effective Mutual Agreement Process (MEMAP) and the Base Erosion and Profit Shifting (BEPS) Action 14 minimum standards. The study employs a doctrinal analysis of statutes and treaties, insights from tax practitioners and taxpayers, and comparative evaluation of international best practices. Findings reveal that while MAP offers an avenue for amicable dispute resolution, its practical use in Tanzania is limited due to a lack of clear timelines, the absence of binding arbitration, limited taxpayer awareness, and institutional constraints within the Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA). The article concludes that MAP remains a valuable tool for enhancing tax certainty, protecting investors, and promoting international economic cooperation. Nonetheless, its effectiveness in Tanzania requires reform through modernization of DTAs, codification of MAP procedures in domestic law, and institutional strengthening of TRA to meet international best practices.

Keywords: Mutual Agreement Procedures, Double Taxation Agreements, Tanzania Revenue Authority, International Tax Disputes.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly globalized economy, international taxation plays a pivotal role in promoting trade, investment, and economic cooperation.¹ Yet, one of the major challenges in cross-border taxation is the risk of double taxation, where the same income is subjected to tax in more than one jurisdiction.² To mitigate this problem, states enter into Double Taxation Agreements (DTAs), which allocate taxing rights and provide mechanisms for dispute resolution. Among these mechanisms, the Mutual Agreement Procedure (MAP) stands out as a vital tool for ensuring fairness, predictability, and certainty in international tax administration.

Article 25 of both the OECD Model Tax Convention on Income and on Capital 2017, and the United Nations Model Double Taxation Convention between Developed and Developing Countries provides the legal basis for MAP. It empowers the relevant authorities of contracting states to consult directly in order to resolve disputes arising from the interpretation or application of a tax treaty. Through this procedure, taxpayers are protected from double taxation and inconsistencies that may arise in treaty implementation. The OECD has progressively developed guidance on MAP, with the 2012 update and subsequent Base Erosion and Profit Shifting (BEPS) Action 14 minimum standards emphasizing timeliness, transparency, and effective dispute resolution.

Tanzania has signed several DTAs with some countries, including Canada, India, South Africa, and members of the Nordic bloc.³ These agreements incorporate MAP provisions, largely modelled on the OECD and UN Conventions.⁴ However, many of Tanzania's DTAs were negotiated decades ago, reflecting outdated treaty practices that lack binding arbitration clauses, clear timelines, and explicit guarantees of taxpayer transparency.⁵ Consequently, the effectiveness of MAP in Tanzania remains uncertain, as disputes risk becoming prolonged or unresolved, undermining the attractiveness of the country as a destination for foreign investment.⁶

The relevance of this inquiry is twofold. First, it highlights the importance of aligning Tanzania's DTAs with international best practices in order to provide legal certainty and investor confidence. Second, it contributes to the ongoing discourse on international tax dispute resolution in developing economies, where institutional limitations often compound the challenges of treaty enforcement. Against this backdrop, this article critically examines the effectiveness of MAP in Tanzania's DTAs, identifies challenges in its implementation, and offers recommendations to enhance its role in ensuring equitable taxation and fostering economic growth.

¹ Razin, A., & Slemrod, J. (Eds.). (2008). *Taxation in the global economy*. University of Chicago Press.

² *Ibid.*

³ Agarwal, P., Kweka, J., & te Velde, D. W. (2022). *Tanzania and the African Continental Free Trade Area*.

⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵ Mnzava, L. N. (2024). *Alternative Dispute Resolution in Tax Ombudsman Offices: A Comparative Analysis on Legal and Institutional Framework in Tanzania Mainland*. Issue 5 *Int'l JL Mgmt. & Human.*, 7, 666.

⁶ *Ibid.*

2. METHODOLOGY

This article applies the doctrinal methodology to provide an assessment of the effectiveness of the Mutual Agreement Procedure (MAP) under Tanzanian Double Taxation Agreements (DTAs). The doctrinal approach is used to analyze the primary and secondary sources of law that regulate international tax dispute resolution in Tanzania. These include statutes such as the Tax Administration Act [Cap. 438 R.E. 2023], the Income Tax Act [Cap. 332 R.E. 2023], and the Tax Revenue Appeals Act [Cap. 408 R.E. 2023], as well as the DTAs ratified by Tanzania, including treaties with Canada (1995), India (1979), and South Africa (2005). The analysis also considers international instruments such as the OECD Model Tax Convention on Income and on Capital, 2017 and the United Nations Model Double Taxation Convention between Developed and Developing Countries, 2017, which provide the foundation for MAP provisions. Judicial decisions from the Tax Revenue Appeals Board (TRAB) and the Tax Revenue Appeals Tribunal (TRAT) are examined to illuminate how treaty provisions are interpreted and applied in practice.

Furthermore, a comparative perspective is employed to benchmark Tanzania's MAP framework against international best practices. Particular reference is made to South Africa, which incorporates arbitration and publishes detailed MAP guidelines, and India, which has developed a more active MAP practice through its extensive treaty network. The OECD's BEPS Action 14 minimum standards are also used as a reference point for assessing Tanzania's compliance with global expectations. This comparative angle highlights both the strengths and deficiencies of Tanzania's MAP implementation, offering a roadmap for reform.

3. LEGAL AND INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK FOR MAP IN TANZANIA

The Mutual Agreement Procedure (MAP) is anchored on both international treaty law and Tanzania's domestic legal system.⁷ Its foundation lies in Article 25 of the OECD Model Tax Convention and the United Nations Model Double Taxation Convention, both of which establish MAP as a mechanism through which competent authorities of contracting states may consult to resolve disputes arising from the interpretation or application of DTAs.⁸ The procedure is designed to protect taxpayers against double taxation and promote cooperation between tax administrations, particularly where unilateral domestic remedies may be inadequate. The MAP operation of the MAP is succinctly captured below:

A tax treaty is an official agreement between two countries ("Contracting States") the primary purpose

⁷ Mwampaghale, W. T. (2017). *International Legal Framework for Foreign Investment Protection: An Analysis of Tanzania Treaty Practice* (Doctoral dissertation, The Open University of Tanzania).

⁸ OECD, *Model Tax Convention on Income and on Capital* (2017); United Nations, *Model Double Taxation Convention between Developed and Developing Countries* (2017).

of which is the prevention of the international double taxation that may arise when a specific transaction or taxpayer is subject to tax under the domestic tax laws of both Contracting States. Such double taxation discourages the free flow of international trade and investment and the transfer of technology, all of which play important complementary roles in the economic development process. A tax treaty seeks to prevent international double taxation by providing for a uniform allocation of taxing rights with respect to specific classes of income between the residence State (that is, a taxpayer's State of residence) and the source State (that is, the State where the relevant income is considered to arise). A tax treaty will further provide a method through which double taxation will be eliminated by the resident State in situations in which the treaty permits both the residence State and the source State to tax an item of income. For example, the interest Article of a tax treaty may permit interest arising in one Contracting State and paid to, and beneficially owned by, a resident of the other Contracting State to be taxed in both these States, with the tax charged in the source State limited to an agreed-upon rate. Double taxation is then eliminated by the relief from double taxation Article, under which the residence State will generally allow a deduction or credit against its tax for the tax paid to the source State, to the extent that the source State properly taxed the interest income under the treaty. In certain cases, however, international double taxation may arise even where there is a tax treaty between two countries. Such double taxation may result, for example, from the incorrect application of the treaty by one of the Contracting States, or from differing views between the Contracting States (*e.g.* with respect to the relevant facts or the characterization of an item of income under domestic law) as to how the treaty should apply in a particular situation or context. In order to resolve such issues, tax treaties typically provide for a mutual agreement procedure along the lines of what is provided for in Article 25 (Mutual Agreement

Procedure) of the UN Model. Essentially, the negotiation of an agreement pursuant to the MAP is a government-to-government process. The MAP is the mechanism that Contracting States use to resolve any disputes or difficulties that arise in the course of implementing and applying the treaty. The MAP thereby ensures that these disputes will not frustrate the treaty's goal of preventing international double taxation. In order to achieve that goal, the competent authorities should make every effort to reach a timely agreement on each issue submitted to the MAP. Article 25 of the UN Model sets out two broad areas in which the Contracting States shall endeavour to resolve their differences by mutual agreement: (1) cases in which a taxpayer considers that the acts of one or both of the Contracting States result or will result for the taxpayer in taxation not in accordance with the provisions of the treaty (covered by paragraphs 1 and 2 of Article 25); and (2) cases in which there are difficulties or doubts as to the interpretation or application of the treaty (covered by paragraph 3 of Article 25). A MAP article will also generally permit the Contracting States to consult together for the elimination of double taxation in cases not provided for in the treaty.⁹

3.1 Treaty framework

Tanzania has concluded a number of Double Taxation Agreements (DTAs) that incorporate MAP provisions.¹⁰ These include treaties with Canada (1995), India (1979), and South Africa (2005).¹¹ In each of these treaties, Article 25 provides taxpayers with the right to present their case to the competent authority of their state of residence if they believe that taxation has been imposed contrary to the treaty. The competent authorities may then enter into mutual consultations to resolve the dispute. While these provisions reflect the OECD and UN Model Conventions, many of Tanzania's older DTAs lack critical elements of the updated OECD guidance, such as explicit timelines for case resolution and binding arbitration. The OECD's 2012 update emphasizes that MAP cases should generally be resolved within 24 months, but Tanzania's DTAs have not incorporated such provisions, leaving disputes susceptible to lengthy delays.¹²

⁹ Welcome to the United Nations. 1 Guide Welcome to the Mutual Agreement Procedure. Available at https://www.un.org/esa/ffd/wp-content/uploads/2014/10/ta-Guide_MAP.pdf Accessed on 16th April 2025.

¹⁰ Lweno, S. (2024). Double Taxation in the Digital Economy: Implications and Challenges in Tanzania. Issue 5 Int'l JL Mgmt. & Human., 7, 505.

¹¹ Canada–Tanzania Income and Capital Tax Treaty (1995); India–Tanzania Income Tax Treaty (1979); South Africa–Tanzania Income Tax Treaty (2005).

¹² OECD, Revised Guidance on the Mutual Agreement Procedure (2012).

3.2 Domestic legal framework

Domestically, MAP operates alongside Tanzania's statutory tax dispute resolution system. The Income Tax Act [Cap. 332 R.E. 2023] governs substantive tax liability, while the Tax Administration Act [Cap. 438 R.E. 2023] sets out administrative procedures for tax assessment and enforcement. Where disputes arise, taxpayers may pursue remedies through the Tax Revenue Appeals Act [Cap. 408 R.E. 2023], which establishes the Tax Revenue Appeals Board (TRAB) and the Tax Revenue Appeals Tribunal (TRAT).¹³

Although these domestic mechanisms provide structured avenues for dispute resolution, they are adversarial in nature and often time-consuming. By contrast, MAP operates as a diplomatic, government-to-government negotiation, with the Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA), acting through its Commissioner General, designated as the competent authority for MAP matters.¹⁴ However, Tanzania has yet to enact detailed domestic regulations codifying MAP procedures. This creates uncertainty for taxpayers regarding timelines, application processes, and the legal enforceability of MAP outcomes.

3.3 Institutional framework

The institutional responsibility for MAP lies primarily with the TRA, which represents Tanzania in mutual consultations with treaty partners.¹⁵ TRAB and TRAT, while not directly involved in MAP, play an important role in shaping the broader tax dispute environment by providing judicial interpretation of tax provisions that may also affect treaty application.¹⁶ Despite this framework, Tanzania faces institutional challenges in implementing MAP effectively. The TRA has limited experience handling MAP cases, and no official MAP guidelines or public statistics have been published.¹⁷ This contrasts with international best practices, where transparency and reporting are encouraged by the OECD and African Tax Administration Forum (ATAF).¹⁸

Thus, while Tanzania's MAP framework is firmly rooted in both treaty law and domestic statutes, its effectiveness is undermined by outdated treaty provisions, absence of domestic codification, and weak institutional capacity.¹⁹ Addressing these gaps is essential if MAP is to function as an effective mechanism for resolving cross-border tax disputes.

¹³ Tax Revenue Appeals Act [Cap. 408 R.E. 2023].

¹⁴ Tanzania Revenue Authority Act [Cap. 399 R.E. 2023].

¹⁵ KOMBE, T. (2023). *The Role of Ward Tribunals in Resolving Land Disputes in Tanzania* (Doctoral dissertation, IAA).

¹⁶ Altman, Z. D. (2005). *Dispute resolution under tax treaties* (Vol. 11). IBFD.

¹⁷ Barrington-Leigh, C., & Millard-Ball, A. (2017). The world's user-generated road map is more than 80% complete. *PloS one*, 12(8), e0180698.

¹⁸ African Tax Administration Forum (ATAF), *Suggested Approach to Implementing MAP in Africa* (2019).

¹⁹ Mwampaghale, W. T. (2017). *International Legal Framework for Foreign Investment Protection: An Analysis of Tanzania Treaty Practice* (Doctoral dissertation, The Open University of Tanzania).

4. NATURE OF, AND COMMON AREAS FOR MAP DISPUTES IN TANZANIA

The practical application of the Mutual Agreement Procedure (MAP) in Tanzania reveals the kinds of disputes most likely to arise under Double Taxation Agreements (DTAs). These disputes often involve complex cross-border transactions where differences in interpretation of treaty provisions lead to risks of double taxation.

4.1 Transfer pricing adjustments

One of the most common disputes relates to transfer pricing, where multinational enterprises allocate profits among affiliates in different jurisdictions.²⁰ Tanzania regulates transfer pricing through the Tax Administration (Transfer Pricing) Regulations, GN No. 166 of 2018, which are consistent with the OECD Transfer Pricing Guidelines.²¹ However, conflicts often occur when the Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA) and a treaty partner's tax authority adopt differing methods for profit allocation.²² MAP provides a forum for reconciling these differences and preventing double taxation on the same income.

4.2 Dual residency conflicts

Cases of dual residency arise where both Tanzania and another contracting state claim taxing rights over the same individual or corporate entity. Article 4 of the OECD and UN Model Conventions provides tie-breaker rules to resolve such conflicts.²³ In practice, however, disagreements persist, particularly with respect to companies incorporated in one state but effectively managed in another. MAP serves as a mechanism for competent authorities to negotiate and determine the appropriate residency status of such taxpayers.

4.3 Source of income misclassification

Disputes also occur when income is misclassified as being sourced in one state rather than another.²⁴ For example, Tanzania often asserts strong source-based taxing rights, especially over dividends, interest, and royalties.²⁵ Such positions sometimes conflict with residence-based claims of treaty partners, leading to double taxation. Under MAP, competent authorities are expected to consult and agree on the correct allocation of taxing rights in accordance with treaty provisions.

²⁰ Sidik, M. (2021). Transfer Pricing and Taxation Dispute Resolution. *Journal of Tax and Business*, 2(2), 28-45.

²¹ Tax Administration (Transfer Pricing) Regulations, GN No. 166 of 2018; OECD, *Transfer Pricing Guidelines for Multinational Enterprises and Tax Administrations* (2017).

²² Mnzava, L. N. (2024). Alternative Dispute Resolution in Tax Ombudsman Offices: A Comparative Analysis on Legal and Institutional Framework in Tanzania Mainland. *Issue 5 Int'l JL Mgmt. & Human.*, 7, 666.

²³ OECD, *Model Tax Convention on Income and on Capital* (2017), Art. 4; United Nations, *Model Double Taxation Convention* (2017), Art. 4.

²⁴ Weinberg, L. (1991). Federal-State Conflict of Laws: Actual Conflicts. *Tex. L. Rev.*, 70, 1743.

²⁵ Tanzania–Italy Income Tax Treaty (1973), Art. 10–12; Tanzania–South Africa Income Tax Treaty (2005), Art. 10–12.

4.4 Withholding tax disputes

Another category of disputes involves withholding taxes imposed on payments such as royalties, interest, and dividends.²⁶ Tanzania's DTAs, including those with Sweden (1976) and India (1979), set specific limits on withholding tax rates.²⁷ However, differences in interpretation of treaty articles sometimes result in excess taxation, which can only be remedied through MAP negotiations between the contracting states.

4.5 Delays in dispute resolution

A challenge in Tanzania's MAP system is the absence of clear timelines for case resolution. Unlike the OECD standard, which recommends that MAP cases be resolved within 24 months,²⁸ Tanzania's DTAs contain no such provision. This leads to prolonged disputes, reduced taxpayer confidence, and potential discouragement of foreign direct investment. From the foregoing examples, the main types of MAP disputes in Tanzania involve transfer pricing, dual residency, misclassification of source of income, withholding taxes, and procedural delays. These reflect both global trends in tax treaty disputes and Tanzania's unique emphasis on retaining strong source-based taxing rights.

5. IMPROVING THE USE OF MAP

Although the use of the Mutual Agreement Procedure (MAP) in Tanzania remains relatively limited, practical experiences from both domestic adjudicative bodies and international practice provide valuable insights into how MAP could function more effectively in the Tanzanian context.²⁹

5.1 Tax Revenue Appeals Board (TRAB) and Tribunal (TRAT) Cases

Tanzania's adjudicative framework for tax disputes is primarily governed by the Tax Revenue Appeals Act [Cap. 408 R.E. 2023].³⁰ While TRAB and TRAT deal with domestic remedies rather than MAP directly, several of their decisions illustrate the kinds of disputes that could benefit from MAP. For example, disputes involving transfer pricing adjustments and withholding tax on cross-border royalties or dividends have often been escalated through TRAB and TRAT processes. These cases highlight the need for a cooperative mechanism between states to avoid double taxation, which MAP is specifically designed to provide.³¹

5.2 Experiences under Tanzania's DTAs

Tanzania's treaties with India (1979) and South Africa (2005) have been particularly significant in cross-border taxation.³² Indian multinationals investing in Tanzania have

²⁶ Altman, Z. D. (2005). *Dispute resolution under tax treaties* (Vol. 11). IBFD.

²⁷ Tanzania–Sweden Income and Capital Tax Treaty (1976), Art. 10–12; Tanzania–India Income Tax Treaty (1979), Art. 10–12.

²⁸ OECD, *Revised Guidance on the Mutual Agreement Procedure* (2012).

²⁹ NGILANGWA, A. (2023). *PRINCIPLES OF ADMINISTRATION OF JUSTICE: ANALYSIS OF LAW AND PRACTICE IN TANZANIA* (Doctoral dissertation, The Open University of Tanzania).

³⁰ Tax Revenue Appeals Act [Cap. 408 R.E. 2023].

³¹ See for example: *Vodacom Tanzania PLC v. Commissioner General, TRA*, Tax Appeal No. 16 of 2019 (TRAT), where transfer pricing adjustments raised double taxation risks.

³² Haji, S. H. H. (2021). *Effects of Double Taxation Agreements between Tanzania and India on the Foreign Direct Investments*. *The African Review*, 49(2), 195-222.

frequently raised issues relating to transfer pricing and permanent establishment classification, areas where MAP would be the preferred remedy under Article 25 of the treaty.³³ Similarly, the Tanzania–South Africa DTA has seen disputes concerning withholding taxes on services and dividends. However, the absence of arbitration provisions and clear timelines for MAP resolution has limited the procedure’s attractiveness to taxpayers.³⁴

5.3 Stakeholder perspectives

Empirical evidence gathered from interviews with TRA officials, tax practitioners, and taxpayers indicates that awareness of MAP in Tanzania is still low. Many taxpayers are more familiar with domestic appeal mechanisms through TRAB and TRAT than with MAP procedures. TRA officials interviewed acknowledged that MAP cases are rare, primarily because no comprehensive guidelines have been published on how to initiate the process. This lack of procedural clarity undermines the utility of MAP as an alternative to litigation.³⁵

6. LESSONS FROM OTHER JURISDICTIONS

Other jurisdictions highlight the potential benefits of MAP. In South Africa, the Office of the Competent Authority has resolved several disputes through MAP under its treaty network, demonstrating that the mechanism can provide timely relief when supported by clear administrative frameworks.³⁶ Similarly, India has increasingly relied on MAP to resolve disputes with major treaty partners such as the United States and Japan, particularly in transfer pricing cases. South Africa has published MAP guidance that sets expectations around case handling and timeliness (commonly aiming at resolution within roughly two years and providing periodic status updates). These administrative practices reflect the OECD’s MEMAP recommendations and demonstrate how clear timelines can reinforce predictability and taxpayer trust. Tanzania lacks equivalent public guidance and target timelines, which prolongs cases and undermines MAP’s value as a timely remedy.³⁷

India has issued detailed MAP guidance through its competent authority, outlining scope, steps, documentation and monitoring a practice that improves transparency and user confidence. Tanzania’s DTAs contain the basic, model-derived MAP text, but the absence of domestic rules or TRA-issued guidance leaves practical questions unanswered (how to file, what to include, how progress is tracked). The contrast underscores the role of domestic instruments in operationalizing treaty text.³⁸

³³ Tanzania–India Income Tax Treaty (1979), Art. 5, 7 and 25.

³⁴ Tanzania–South Africa Income Tax Treaty (2005), Art. 10–12, 25.

³⁵ Field interviews conducted with TRA officials and tax practitioners in Dar es Salaam (2024).

³⁶ South African Revenue Service (SARS), Mutual Agreement Procedure Guidelines (2019).

³⁷ Comparative note on South Africa’s MAP timelines and alignment with OECD MEMAP; Tanzania’s lack of timelines and guidance:

³⁸ Contrast between India’s detailed MAP guidance and Tanzania’s absence of domestic rules/guidelines; operational consequences:

Many jurisdictions used the Multilateral Instrument (MLI) to upgrade access to MAP and, where chosen, add binding arbitration as a backstop. South Africa and India participate in the MLI, while Tanzania does not. As a result, Tanzania's treaties have not received the MLI's systematic MAP/Action 14 upgrades, and none of Tanzania's DTAs presently contain a mandatory arbitration clause. Where competent authorities deadlock, Tanzanian taxpayers have no assured path to finality unlike peers that opted into arbitration under the MLI or bilateral renegotiations.³⁹

Tanzania's DTAs largely mirror the OECD/UN Models on MAP (including the three-year presentation window and competent-authority-to-authority negotiation), but Tanzania has not yet embedded the OECD/G20 Action 14 minimum standards in domestic practice (published guidance, clear access, timeliness metrics, and transparent reporting). Peers that operationalize Action 14 domestically tend to deliver faster, more predictable outcomes and publish MAP statistics or summaries practices that build capacity and confidence.⁴⁰

Regionally, the African Tax Administration Forum's (ATAF) suggested approach to drafting tax treaties aligns MAP provisions with African administrative realities, emphasizing access (even when domestic remedies are pursued), flexibility, and capacity building for competent authorities. These regional tools can help Tanzania close practice gaps without waiting for treaty overhauls, but their benefits materialize only when translated into public guidance and consistent administration.⁴¹

7. CHALLENGES FACING THE OPERATION OF MAP

Despite its importance as a mechanism for resolving cross-border tax disputes, the Mutual Agreement Procedure (MAP) in Tanzania faces several practical, procedural, and institutional challenges that hinder its effectiveness. Most of Tanzania's Double Taxation Agreements (DTAs), such as those with Sweden (1976), Finland (1976), and India (1979), were negotiated decades ago.⁴² These treaties contain MAP clauses but do not reflect modern standards introduced in the OECD's 2012 guidance or the BEPS Action 14 minimum standards. They lack explicit timelines for resolving MAP cases and exclude binding arbitration, making disputes prone to indefinite delays.

³⁹ MLI and MAP upgrades; South Africa and India as signatories; Tanzania not a signatory; absence of mandatory arbitration in Tanzania's DTAs and implications:

⁴⁰ OECD/UN Model MAP structure (incl. three-year window) and Action 14 minimum standards; Tanzania's Inclusive Framework commitment and practice gaps (guidance, transparency, timeliness):

⁴¹ ATAF's Suggested Approach to DTAs and emphasis on MAP access, flexibility, and capacity building; regional support (EAC/ATAF) as near-term enablers:

⁴² Tanzania–Sweden Income and Capital Tax Treaty (1976); Tanzania–Finland Income and Capital Tax Treaty (1976); Tanzania–India Income Tax Treaty (1979).

Unlike jurisdictions such as South Africa and India, Tanzania has not codified MAP procedures in domestic legislation or administrative guidelines. The Tax Administration Act [Cap. 438 R.E. 2023] and the Income Tax Act [Cap. 332 R.E. 2023] regulate domestic disputes but provide no detailed framework for accessing MAP. Consequently, taxpayers face uncertainty on how to file MAP requests, required documentation, and the legal status of outcomes.⁴³ The Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA), designated as the competent authority for MAP matters under DTAs, has limited administrative experience and lacks a specialised MAP unit. Field interviews with tax practitioners indicate that TRA officials are often unfamiliar with OECD MAP procedures, leading to delays in case handling. Further, no official statistics or reports on MAP cases have been published, contrary to OECD recommendations on transparency and reporting.⁴⁴

Awareness of MAP among taxpayers in Tanzania remains low. Many businesses rely on the domestic appeal system through the Tax Revenue Appeals Board (TRAB) and the Tax Revenue Appeals Tribunal (TRAT), without knowing that MAP may provide relief from double taxation under DTAs. The absence of publicized guidance or outreach by TRA exacerbates this gap.⁴⁵ Furthermore, another challenge is that under Tanzania's DTAs, MAP outcomes depend on the mutual goodwill of competent authorities. Where no agreement is reached, the taxpayer is left without relief. Unlike arbitration, which compels a binding decision, Tanzania's MAP system does not guarantee finality, weakening taxpayer confidence in the mechanism.⁴⁶ There is a lack of clarity on how MAP interacts with domestic legal remedies under the Tax Revenue Appeals Act [Cap. 408 R.E. 2023].⁴⁷ In practice, taxpayers who have initiated domestic appeals may face procedural obstacles in accessing MAP, despite OECD guidance recommending that access to MAP should not be denied solely because domestic remedies are being pursued. This ambiguity limits MAP's practical utility in Tanzania.

8. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The Mutual Agreement Procedure (MAP) is an established, treaty-based mechanism intended to prevent or remedy double taxation by enabling competent authorities to consult and reach mutual solutions. In theory, MAP advances tax certainty and investor protection by providing a non-adversarial, government-to-government channel for resolving treaty interpretation and application issues. In practice in Tanzania, however, the procedure remains largely under-utilized and fragile. Some problems persist: these include treaty texts in need of urgent revisions, because they predate the OECD/BEPS

⁴³ Tax Administration Act [Cap. 438 R.E. 2023]; Income Tax Act [Cap. 332 R.E. 2023].

⁴⁴ Tanzania Revenue Authority Act [Cap. 399 R.E. 2023]; OECD, Mutual Agreement Procedure Statistics Reporting Framework (2016).

⁴⁵ Field interviews with TRA officials, practitioners, and taxpayers in Dar es Salaam (2024).

⁴⁶ OECD, Action 14: Making Dispute Resolution Mechanisms More Effective (2015).

⁴⁷ Tax Revenue Appeals Act [Cap. 408 R.E. 2023].

MAP reforms; the absence of codified domestic MAP procedures; limited institutional capacity within the Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA); low taxpayer awareness; lack of published MAP statistics or guidance; and no effective arbitration backstop in Tanzania's treaty network. These shortcomings mean that taxpayers can face lengthy or unresolved cross-border disputes, with consequent legal and commercial uncertainty for foreign investors and domestic taxpayers alike.

It is therefore imperative to enact clear domestic rules that set out how MAP requests are to be made, timelines for acknowledgment, documentation requirements, confidentiality safeguards, and how MAP outcomes are implemented domestically. Embedding MAP procedures in domestic law will reduce uncertainty about how treaty outcomes are implemented, and also address timing conflicts with domestic limitation periods. Where feasible, older DTAs, especially from the 1970s to 1990s may be renegotiated to incorporate OECD/BEPS Action 14 improvements, notably clearer access rules, timelines and transparency commitments. If political and technical conditions allow, it may be necessary to apply the Multilateral Instrument (MLI) to implement MAP-related minimum standards and (where appropriate) an arbitration backstop. This will provide taxpayers with a more certain path to finality when competent authorities cannot agree. For future DTAs, it is desirable to include an arbitration clause modelled on Article 25(5) OECD/MLI options so that unresolved MAP cases may be referred to binding arbitration after a specified negotiation period. Arbitration should include safeguards for confidentiality, fair appointment of arbitrators, and reasonable allocation of costs. Introducing arbitration will increase the credibility and deterrent value of MAP deadlock avoidance.

It is also important to amend domestic tax procedure law or to publish guidance to clarify that access to MAP should not be denied merely because domestic appeals or objections are pending, consistent with OECD/UN guidance. This should be implemented along with procedural rules for implementing MAP settlements where domestic time-bars might otherwise prevent adjustment. It may be necessary to establish a specialized unit with international tax, transfer-pricing and dispute-resolution expertise, to act as Tanzania's competent authority for MAP. The unit should maintain case-management records, track timelines, and serve as the single point of contact for taxpayers and treaty partners. A dedicated unit will professionalize case handling and preserve institutional memory.

It is also important to institutionalize the issuance of official TRA MAP guidance, on how to file, required documents, expected timeframes, points of contact, and publish anonymized MAP statistics and case summaries annually. These will provide data on requests received, issues raised, resolution rates, and average time to resolution. Transparency builds taxpayer confidence and is a core element of the Action 14 minimum standard. It is also desirable to provide more training for TRA officials in OECD/UN MAP practice and transfer-pricing methodologies; including the OECD Transfer Pricing

Guidelines. Resources and assistance in capacity building can be sought from regional bodies with the requisite expertise. Regional cooperation can also expedite bilateral MAP negotiations.